

EXPLORING TARGET-BASED SCREENING, MOLECULAR DYNAMICS SIMULATION AND PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS FOR DRUG REPURPOSING IN NUT MIDLINE CARCINOMA

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Abstract. *NUT Midline Carcinoma (NMC), a particularly malignant and invasive cancer resulting from the fusion of NUT and BRD4 genes, produces a fusion protein that influences cell growth and regulates transcription. Deregulation of this protein has been observed in numerous cancers. The BD1 domain of BRD4-containing proteins has been demonstrated binding to acetylated lysine residues on histone proteins, thereby impacting gene expression and chromatin remodeling. The DrugRep database was used for target-based screening (TBS) of FDA-approved drugs. CurPocket, an integrated tool in DrugRep, was employed to automatically identify potential binding pockets, and docking was performed using AutoDock Vina 1.1.2. SwissADME tools were used to assess pharmacokinetics and drug-likeness attributes. Additionally, the GROMACS and Galaxy platforms were employed for the MD simulations and principal component analysis, respectively. The TBS technique was employed to evaluate 100 drug candidates for human intestinal absorption and blood-brain barrier permeability using the Egan-Egg model. Eighty-four met the filtration criteria and the drug-likeness models narrowed the pool to 48. Toxicophoric parameters, including the PAINS and Brenk alerts, further refined the subset of potential drugs to 39. The lead-likeness criteria identified five drugs, which were evaluated based on binding free energy and hydrogen bond analysis. MD simulation and PCA facilitated more in-depth evaluations, ultimately leading to the selection of ataluren as a potential repurposed NMC drug.*

1. Introduction

Dysregulation of BRD4 is increasingly observed in colorectal, breast, pancreatic, and lung cancers, highlighting its role in cancer development. Tandem bromodomain 1 (BD1) of BRD4 is critical for binding acetylated lysine residues on histone proteins, contributing to gene expression and chromatin remodeling [1,2,3]. Bromodomains are integral to DNA replication, cell cycle control, DNA repair, chromatin remodeling, and transcriptional regulation, facilitating the assembly of nuclear macromolecular complexes at specific chromatin sites [4].

Bromodomain-containing proteins are key for the development of potent and specific BRD inhibitors. BETs significantly influence tumorigenesis by regulating the expression of genes essential for tumor growth and survival [5]. However, resistance to BET inhibitors remains a challenge, necessitating new strategies. This study examined the TBS of FDA-approved drugs by

using the DrugRep database (<http://cao.labshare.cn/drugrep/>). The selection criteria focused on their relevance to BRD4 inhibition and their potential therapeutic significance in NMC. We employed bioinformatics and computational tools, including molecular docking software, such as AutoDock Vina, and dynamic simulation tools, such as GROMACS, to analyze pharmacokinetics, drug-likeness features, molecular docking, and dynamic simulations. This comparative study aimed to evaluate the efficacy and safety of selected drugs targeting BRD4 for NMC treatment. Using these techniques, we thoroughly assessed the pharmacological and structural aspects of these compounds, thereby contributing to a comprehensive understanding of their potential therapeutic value in NMC

2. Methods and Materials

Preparation and Energy Minimization of Target Protein

We obtained the crystal structure of human BRD4 (PDB ID: 7REK) at a resolution of 1.20 Å from the RCSB PDB database [6]. To prepare the protein for docking analysis, we extracted the apo form of the protein using SwissPDB viewer, excluding heteroatoms, ions, and additional molecules. Energy minimization was performed to improve the conformation and structural integrity of the target protein. This process involves refining the protein structure to reduce unfavorable interactions and stabilize the molecule. The aim was to obtain a more accurate representation of the native state of the protein for subsequent computational analyses [7,8,9].

Target-based Virtual Screening

We employed the DrugRep online platform (<http://cao.labshare.cn/drugrep/>) to acquire and process the compound libraries. This platform offers the ability to retrieve and dock compounds from three separate libraries: an approved drug library, an experimental drug library, and a traditional Chinese medicine library. Our primary emphasis was on the approved drug library, which we used for conducting TBS.

ADME Profiling of TBS compounds

The ligands identified by TBS were evaluated based on several ADME parameters, including assessments of Human Intestinal Absorption (HIA) and Blood-Brain Barrier (BBB) permeability [10]. Moreover, drug likeness was evaluated using criteria such as Lipinski's Rule of Five (RO5), Ghose, Veber, Egan, and Muegge parameters [11,12,13,14]. Medicinal chemistry attributes, including PAINS and Brenk alerts, as well as lead-likeness parameters assessed using the SwissADME web tool, were taken into consideration [15,16].

Shortlisting of Drug Candidates using ΔG and Hydrogen Bond Criteria

We emphasized the role of hydrogen bonds in molecular recognition and binding specificity by utilizing metrics such as ΔG and hydrogen bond formation to identify potential candidates for ADME-sifted drugs [17].

MD Simulation of BRD4 Docked Complexes with Top Drug Candidates

Molecular dynamics simulations were carried out on complexes formed by the human BRD4 protein, with the top four drugs exhibiting the lowest ΔG and at least one hydrogen bond. Simulations were executed at 300 K using the MM level within the GROMACS package, version 5.1.2 [18].

Principal Component Analysis

To explore the complex interactions and conformational changes that occur between proteins and drugs, we utilized the analytical tool of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) within the Galaxy platform (<https://usegalaxy.eu/>). By employing PCA, we were able to identify and

highlight statistically significant conformations within the 10 ns trajectory of human BRD4 and selected drug molecules [19,20].

Results and Discussion

Target-Based Virtual Screening Analysis

Using human BRD4 as the template in the DrugRep database, a list of the top 100 compounds based on their binding propensities was generated. This carefully curated dataset was derived from an in-house compilation of FDA-approved libraries comprising a total of 2,315 drugs.

Evaluation of Druglikeness in Compounds Meeting HIA and BBB Permeation Criteria

The SwissADME tool utilizes five distinct sets of pharmaceutical- and biotechnology-based rules, each consisting of various filters that provide qualitative predictions regarding a molecule's potential as an oral drug candidate in terms of bioavailability. These rules encompass Pfizer's Rule of Five (RO5) criteria (molecular weight ≤ 500 , hydrogen bond donors ≤ 5 , hydrogen bond acceptors ≤ 10 , $\log P \leq 5$) [11], Amgen's Ghose filters ($160 \leq$ molecular weight ≤ 480 , $-0.4 \leq$ WLogP ≤ 5.6 , $40 \leq$ molecular refractivity ≤ 130 , $20 \leq$ atom count ≤ 70) [12], GlaxoSmithKline's Veber filters (rotatable bonds ≤ 10 , topological polar surface area ≤ 140) [13], Pharmacia's Egan parameters (WLogP ≤ 5.88 , topological polar surface area ≤ 131.6), and Bayer's Muegge filters ($200 \leq$ molecular weight ≤ 600 , $-2 \leq$ XLogP3 ≤ 5 , topological polar surface area ≤ 150 , number of carbons > 4 , number of heteroatoms > 1 , rotatable bonds ≤ 15 , hydrogen bond acceptors ≤ 10 , hydrogen bond donors ≤ 5) [14]. Among the drugs meeting both the HIA and BBB criteria (84 in total), 48 exhibited no violation of the aforementioned models and rules. Furthermore, the reference molecule (R6S) exhibited one breach in the RO5 criterion (MW >500), four breaches in the Ghose filter (MW >480 , WLOGP >5.6 , MR >130 , atom counts >70), and one breach each in the Egan (WLOGP >5.88) and Muegge (XLOGP3 >5) filters.

Free Energy of Binding and Hydrogen Bonding Analysis

Five lead-like compounds, namely estrone, ataluren, perampanel, ergometrine, and exemestane, displayed zero lead-likeness violations. Ataluren exhibited a ΔG value of -9.5 kcal/mol and engaged with 17 residues through five distinct binding interactions (Vdw, 1 hydrogen bond, CHB, Pi-Alkyl, and Pi-Pi T-shaped). Similarly, estrone showed a ΔG value of -9.0 kcal/mol, interacting with 12 residues through Vdw, one hydrogen bond, Alkyl, and Pi-Alkyl interactions. Perampanel, ergometrine, and exemestane demonstrated ΔG values of -8.5 kcal/mol, 8.5 kcal/mol, and 8.2 kcal/mol, respectively. They interacted with 14, 14, and 11 residues, involving Vdw, 1 hydrogen bond, CHB, Pi-Alkyl, and Pi-Sigma interactions for perampanel, five interactions including Vdw, 2 hydrogen bond, CHB, Alkyl, and Pi-Alkyl for ergometrine, and two interactions (Vdw and Alkyl) for exemestane. Furthermore, the control molecule R6S engaged with 18 residues via seven distinct molecular forces having a ΔG value of -8.1 kcal/mol.

Evaluation of Docked Complex Stability through MD Simulation

The interaction between exemestane and the target protein human BRD4 was found to lack hydrogen bonding. Subsequently, the four remaining drugs, ataluren, estrone, perampanel, and ergometrine, were selected for further molecular dynamics simulation studies, as they exhibited hydrogen bonding during docking. The stability of these complexes was assessed through a 10 ns molecular dynamics simulation using the GROMACS package, with RMSD, RMSF, SASA, ΔG_{Solv} , Rg, and HBs graphs plotted for analysis [17,18,20] (Figure 1A-F)

Figure 1A-F: MD simulation plots for selected parameters: A) RMSD, B) RMSF, C) SASA, D) ΔG_{Solv} , E) R_g , F) HBs. The magenta, blue, red, and green curves represent BRD4 in complex with ataluren, estrone, perampanel, and ergometrine, respectively.

Principal Component Analysis

Principal component analysis (PCA) was utilized to evaluate and compare the trajectories of the docked complexes involving ataluren, estrone, perampanel, and ergometrine with human BRD4 [19,20]. PCA analysis of ligand-protein docked complexes involves several mathematical steps. Initially, the data is centered by subtracting the mean of each feature from all data points:

$$X_{\text{centered}} = X - \bar{X}$$

Where X represents the original data matrix, and \bar{X} is the mean of each feature. This centered data matrix is then used to calculate the covariance matrix:

$$\Sigma = \frac{1}{n} (X_{\text{centered}}^T X_{\text{centered}})$$

Where n is the number of samples and T typically represents the transpose operation. Eigenvalue decomposition is performed on this covariance matrix, yielding eigenvectors V and eigenvalues Λ :

$$\Sigma V = V \Lambda$$

These eigenvectors represent the principal components, which are directions of maximum variance in the data. By projecting the centered data onto these eigenvectors, principal components are obtained:

$$PC = X_{\text{centered}}V$$

The proportion of variance explained by PC1 for ataluren (19.6%), estrone (24%), perampanel (25.6%), and ergometrine (24.9%) was indicative of the trajectories associated with each compound. PCA plots depicting the principal components are presented in Figures 2A-D. A lower proportion of variance for PC1 suggested a more constrained or stable trajectory. Thus, ataluren, with the lowest proportion of variance (19.6%), appeared to exhibit a relatively more stable interaction compared to estrone, perampanel, and ergometrine, which had higher proportions of variance in PC1.

Figure 2A: PCA plot for ataluren and BRD4 docked complex.

Figure 2B: PCA plot for estrone and BRD4 docked complex.

Figure 2C: PCA plot for perampanel and BRD4 docked complex.

Figure 2D: PCA plot for ergometrine and BRD4 docked complex.

The investigation demonstrated that ataluren exhibited superior drug-like properties compared to the other compounds examined in the study. It displayed high permeability across the

gastrointestinal tract and blood-brain barrier, fulfilled drug-likeness and lead-likeness criteria, and formed stable noncovalent interactions with key amino acid residues. Molecular dynamics simulations corroborated its stability, with favorable RMSD, RMSF, and SASA values, as well as promising Gibbs Free Energy and PCA results. Although some deviations were observed in unsaturation, ataluren met all other critical parameters, positioning it as a potential therapeutic candidate for NMC.

Conclusion

The extensive analysis conducted in this study consistently demonstrated the favorable characteristics of ataluren across a broad range of parameters, thereby establishing its potential as a promising and stable ligand for human BRD4. These findings strongly suggest the need for further research regarding the incorporation of ataluren into drug development initiatives, specifically those targeting human BRD4 and its relevance to NMC. Although compounds such as estrone, perampanel, and ergometrine also exhibit favorable characteristics, the inherent variability in their stability metrics underscores the importance of employing a multifaceted approach when evaluating ligands for target proteins. It is noteworthy that while ataluren has emerged as a promising repurposed drug candidate against NMC based on *in silico* findings, the necessity for wet-lab validation remains paramount prior to its practical application.

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